

SUSTAINABILITY OF UZBEKISTAN TOURISM AND CLIMATE CHANGE AS A MAIN THREAT

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Abstract. *Although sustainable development and sustainable tourism have been studied since the late 1980s, there are few studies on the relationship between climate, environment and tourism. The Republic of Uzbekistan is a unique country on the Historical Silk Road in terms of culture and natural resources, and tourism is one of the main sources of income for the country, and the relationship between sustainable tourism and climate is of vital importance for the tourism sector of Uzbekistan, which is based on highly sensitive cultural and ecological resources. In this study, climate change in the Republic of Uzbekistan between 1901-2021 was examined based on the World Bank's basic climate indicator data and compared with the 'World Climate Change' data. It is seen that the results of this analysis contain very useful findings in terms of sustainable development and tourism.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan Republic, Sustainability, Tourism, Climate change, Demand, Attractiveness.*

Annotatsiya. *Barqaror rivojlanish va barqaror turizm 1980-yillarning oxiridan boshlab o'rganilgan bo'lsa-da, iqlim, atrof-muhit va turizm o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga oid tadqiqotlar kam. O'zbekiston Respublikasi madaniyati va tabiiy resurslari jihatidan Tarixiy Ipak yo'lida joylashgan noyob davlat bo'lib, turizm mamlakat uchun asosiy daromad manbalaridan biri bo'lib, barqaror turizm va iqlim o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik turizm uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. O'zbekistonning o'ta sezgir madaniy va ekologik resurslarga asoslangan sektori. Ushbu tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasida 1901-2021 yillardagi iqlim o'zgarishi Jahon bankining asosiy iqlim ko'rsatkichlari ma'lumotlari asosida o'rganildi va "Jahon iqlim o'zgarishi" ma'lumotlari bilan solishtirildi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, ushbu tahlil natijalari barqaror rivojlanish va turizm nuqtai nazaridan juda foydali xulosalarni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *O'zbekiston Respublikasi, Barqarorlik, Turizm, Iqlim o'zgarishi, Talab, Jozibadorlik.*

Аннотация. *Хотя устойчивое развитие и устойчивый туризм изучаются с конца 1980-х годов, исследований о взаимосвязи климата, окружающей среды и туризма немного. Республика Узбекистан является уникальной страной на Историческом Шелковом пути с точки зрения культуры и природных ресурсов, а туризм является одним из основных источников дохода для страны. Взаимосвязь между устойчивым туризмом и климатом имеет жизненно важное значение, для туристического сектора Узбекистана, который основан на высококочувствительных культурных и экологических ресурсах. В этом исследовании изменение климата в Республике Узбекистан в период с 1901 по 2021 год было изучено на основе данных основных климатических индикаторов Всемирного банка и сопоставлено с данными «Мирового изменения климата». Видно, что результаты этого*

анализа содержат очень полезные выводы с точки зрения устойчивого развития и туризма.

Ключевые слова: Республика Узбекистан, устойчивость, туризм, изменение климата, спрос, привлекательность.

Introduction. Since the 1980s, sustainable development and sustainable tourism have become popular in research. However, there are very few in-depth studies on the meaning and impact of 'sustainable tourism practices' [5]. Sustainable development and sustainable tourism studies are almost non-existent, especially in sensitive ecological and cultural areas such as Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's climate is arid and continental, with large temperature variations between days and seasons. 79% of the country consists of flat topography, semi-desert steppes or desert regions due to the drying up of the Aral Sea. The remaining southeastern regions, including major cities such as Tashkent and Samarkand, have a continental climate. Therefore, adaptation priorities in Uzbekistan include providing support to key sectors such as agriculture, economy, tourism, water resources management, population health, disaster risk reduction and energy, and understanding the impacts of climate change [2]. The study of highly sensitive eco-cultural systems such as Uzbekistan is extremely valuable, and this study aims to draw attention to this area.

Literature review. In the Brundtland Commission Report (1987), sustainable development was defined as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" [1]. Although the concept of sustainable development is simple, its implementation is difficult and national and international organizations need to be redesigned accordingly. However, there is no significant progress in this regard and a major deterioration is observed in the environment, which is one of the basic elements of sustainability, because of global warming [4]. In this study, it is seen that global warming in Uzbekistan is increasing radically and steadily.

Ecological problems began to be seen largely in the 1970s. People believed that growth was the main cause of environmental degradation. A lifestyle suitable for sustainable development does not prevent economic growth. However, growth is essential for poverty reduction and economic development. For this, at least 3% growth per capita is needed. In addition, poverty reduces people's sustainable use of resources. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt sustainable development methods to societies [4].

Global warming is defined as the increase in combined surface air and sea surface temperatures worldwide over a 30-year period. The critical level of global warming is 1.5°C above the pre-industrial average temperature. Studies on this subject focus on new living and consumption practices, new energy types and technologies globally to reduce the negative effects of climate change. Global warming reached approximately 1°C (probably) 0.8°C to 1.2°C above pre-industrial levels in 2017. The increase is probably increasing between 0.1°C and 0.3°C per decade. Today, the warming criterion is expressed in terms of the period 1850-1900, which is used as an estimate of pre-industrial temperatures. However, many regions and seasons, such as Uzbekistan, have experienced warming above the global average. These regions and seasons, where warming is seen above the world average, are a very important issue and pose a serious threat to sustainable development and tourism [7]. Uzbekistan is one such region and is a highly sensitive ecosystem experiencing warming well above the global warming average. Identifying the global and local factors and rates affecting this critical level of warming in Uzbekistan may be

vital. Therefore, this study is a meaningful starting point. Because tourism practices based on natural and cultural resources create an indispensable economy for the region. It is recommended to conduct more sensitive studies on the effects of global and regional warming on the country's resources. In a study conducted for European countries, it was observed that the climate system and economic effects of +1.5°C global warming occur simultaneously in many sectors. Scientific findings and targets related to sustainability policies should be associated and the effects of +1.5°C and +2°C increases on Uzbekistan and especially the tourism industry should be investigated to adapt to climate change and reduce damages.

Tourism, sustainability, and climate change. Many tourism activities are affected by the climate, from swimming and sunbathing, skiing, water sports and sailing to extreme sports and rehabilitation. In addition, it has an impact on tourism development, tourism investments, the duration and quality of a tourism season and the quantitative and qualitative transformation of space in terms of sustainable development [6]. There are many studies that show that climate change affects the choice of destinations of tourists. Because some destinations will not meet all the needs of tourists and tourists will not want to spend money to visit these destinations. The natural environment is an important resource for the development of tourism and the changes in nature caused by climate change will affect tourism destinations. Foreign tourists are more sensitive to climate comfort than domestic tourists. Relative humidity and precipitation are important conditions for climate comfort level. However, humidity and precipitation are not parameters that can be controlled. Therefore, understanding the expectations of demand and determining the supply conditions accordingly is highly important for the destination. This is especially important when tourism activity is carried out in sensitive areas such as Uzbekistan. It is important to fully understand and manage tourism demand. 81% of global travelers confirm that sustainable travel is important to them, and 50% say recent news about climate change has influenced them to make more sustainable travel choices [10]. The biometeorology literature, in which the five climate variables in the Tourism Climate Index and their weights are expressed, is explained by Mieczkowski (1985) [8, 9]. As sub-indices in the tourism climate index; maximum daily temperature, minimum daily relative humidity, total precipitation, total sunshine hours, average wind speed affect the quality, comfort, duration of tourist experience and tourism expenditures (Table 1).

Any increase in global temperature (e.g. +0.5°C) is predicted to primarily affect human health with negative consequences. It is known that agricultural societies are displaced from their places of residence due to global warming and that a 2°C temperature increase compared to a 1.5°C warming will cause greater economic decline in low- and middle-income countries and regions. The first aim of tourism and climate studies is to determine the potential role of climate change in shaping tourism conditions in specific locations. The second aim is to examine the impacts of climate change on the attractions and environments on which tourism practices depend. Global warming has already affected tourism, with the risks of warming below 1.5°C increasing in certain geographical areas and seasonally [7]. Every 1°C of temperature change moves the Earth's ecoregions by about 100 miles (160 km) – for example, if the climate warms by 4°C over the next century, species in the Northern Hemisphere will need to find a suitable climate regime about 500 km (or 500 m higher), and forests are among the most valuable sources of ecosystem goods and services. 2023 is set to be the hottest year since global records began in 1850, and the 10 hottest years on record have all occurred in the last decade (2014-2023) [3]. Only average temperature values of the basic climate variables classified and produced by the Climate Research

Unit (CRU) of the University of East Anglia (UEA) were used in this study to show the climate change experienced by Uzbekistan in 121 years (1901-2021). At the same time, these data were used to compare the World Climate Change trend and Uzbekistan in the same time (Graph 1).

Table 1: Essential Climate Variables

No	Variable Name	Unit	Description
1	Max-Temperature	°C	Average maximum-temperature
2	Mean Temperature	°C	Average mean temperature
3	Min-Temperature	°C	Average minimum-temperature
4	Precipitation		Precipitation, sum over the identified period.

Source: Harris et al., 2020; 10

Data Analysis and Findings. In this article, average temperatures in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the World between 1901 and 2021 were used. Figure 1 shows the trend of average temperatures in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which shows a certain increase in average temperatures. Accordingly, while the difference between the start and end dates of the world average increase in 121 years is **1.11** degrees Celsius, in Uzbekistan this value is **2.02**. The temperature increase in Uzbekistan is almost twice the world average. The climate change trend in Uzbekistan shows that it is exceeding the critical level of **1.5** degrees Celsius average.

Figure 1: Observed annual average mean surface air temperature 1901-2021 Uzbekistan and the World Source: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan>

Conclusion. Our world and humanity are facing a great danger and threat. Global warming is a declared emergency problem for the planet and there is no place in the world that is immune from this phenomenon. As with all industries, tourism is one of the creators of this problem and will be one of the sectors most affected by this threat. However, the degree of impact is different for each region. In this study, the air temperature values in the Republic of Uzbekistan between 1901-2021 were compared with the world average and the increasing trend was examined, and it was seen that the historical data showed an increase of approximately twice the world average in the geography of the Republic of Uzbekistan and exceeded the critical threshold. It is observed that the increasing trend continues and the increase rates, especially in the last 20 years,

continue to increase. It has been proven that tourism demand is closely related to climate change and directly affects destination preference, length of stay and amount of expenditure. It is recommended to conduct more sensitive studies on the effects of global and regional warming on the country's tourism resources. It is expected that the results of this study will contribute especially to researchers and practitioners who guide tourism policy and planning.

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